

Gender Differences in Indian Library and Information Science Literature: A Bibliometric Analysis

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ABSTRACT

The present study investigates the research productivity and gender disparity in Indian LIS research. The study examines the authorship pattern, research productivity of male and female authors, average growth rate of female authors, and their professional engagements. The study reveals that single-authored papers (33.60%) are dominated by multi-authorship papers (66.39%) in selected Indian LIS journals. The study shows that female authors contributed only 27.34% of articles during 2012-2021 at the same time the male authors contributed 72.65% of articles. The study reveals that the highest Average Growth Rate (AGR) for female authors was recorded in the year 2021 (25.71) and the lowest AGR was for female authors recorded in the year 2014 (-37.09). The study clearly shows that female authors are less productive whether they work at the individual levels or collaborative levels. From the findings of the study, it is found that there exists a gender disparity in Indian LIS research.

KEYWORDS: *Research Productivity, Gender Disparity, LIS Research, Bibliometrics.*

INTRODUCTION

Gender disparity is being increasingly identified in many disciplines including library and information science. Gender Studies is an emerging area of study and because of growth in study and research in the field, literature in this area is developing very fast. The periodicals are the indicators of literature growth in any field of knowledge. They emerge as the main channel for transmitting knowledge. Here Bibliometric analysis can successfully be applied to identify the research trends in the subject, thereby helping to know the growth and development of the subject (Gogoi, 2017). Gender is an important influential factor in research productivity and many studies found that male authors are more productive and progressive in the research fields compared to their female counterparts (Patel, 2019).

It is extensive, yet fragmented, evidence of gender disparities in academia that suggests women are underrepresented in most scientific disciplines and publish fewer articles throughout a career, and their

work acquires fewer citations (Huang, *et al.*, 2020; Rachid, *et al.*, 2021). Globally, women account for fewer than 30% of fractionalized authorships, whereas men represent slightly more than 70%. Women are similarly underrepresented when it comes to first authorships. For every article with a female first author, there are nearly two (1.93) articles first-authored by men (Lariviere, *et al.*, 2013).

However, research productivity is important for building and maintaining a successful academic career. It gives distinguishability to the author and provides a platform and opportunity for recognition as a researcher. It is not only the means through which research is communicated but also a critical measure Bibliometrics: Global gender disparities in the science of academic productivity and merit. The quantity and quality of publications are frequently used to assess job employment, tenure, and promotion (Beasley, Simon, and Wright, 2018; Lee, *et al.*, 2021).

How to cite this paper: Vinay R S | Dr. Sampath Kumar B T "Gender Differences in Indian Library and Information Science Literature: A Bibliometric Analysis" Published in International Journal of Trend in Scientific Research and Development (ijtsrd), ISSN: 2456-6470, Volume-9 | Issue-5, October 2025, pp.1230-1235, URL: www.ijtsrd.com/papers/ijtsrd97445.pdf

IJTSRD97445

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Gender disparities have been demonstrated in academic research in many countries and across the library and information science discipline with male LIS authors usually having more publications, more citations, h-indexes, higher impact factors, and a higher propensity for promotions to higher ranks and female authors having very few publications, citations, h-indexes, and lower impact factors (Gul, *et al.*, 2016; Vinay, Sampath Kumar, Kumbar, 2019; Bisaria, 2019; Chatterjee and Werner, 2021; Bisaria, 2021). Therefore, we aimed to examine the research productivity of male and female authors in the field of library and information science scholarly literature in India.

Review of Literature

Numerous studies have been carried out by various researchers, professionals, and faculty members on gender disparities in library and information science research in India as well as abroad. Previous studies have provided a wide range of explanations for the disparity between women researchers' and men researchers' publication records.

Sampath Kumar, *et al.*, (2018) identified the authorship patterns and gender disparities in the LIS research productivity. The results of the study showed that there is an increasing trend in the publication productivity of Indian authors in LIS research. Most of the articles are published by males (72.30%) and only 27.69% of articles are published by female authors. The study indicated that there is an existed gender disparity in LIS research productivity.

Vinay, Sampath Kumar, and Kumbar (2019) found gender divergence in Indian LIS research. The study showed that co-authorship (67.36%) was predominated over solo authorship (32.64%) in Library and Information Science research. The male authors published more articles (73.33%) than their female counterparts (26.66%). Further, it is found that the contribution of female authors is lower regardless of whether they worked at an individual level (5.97%) or in association with other female authors (6.20%).

Patel and Verma (2019) examined the publication patterns of male and female authors in the SRELS Journal of Information Management. The study revealed that multi authorship pattern is leading in this journal. Male authors are more productive compared to female authors and female authors had few international collaborative papers and female authors' research productivity increased when they collaborated with male authors in their research work.

Lee, *et al.*, (2021) evaluated the gender disparities in the first and last authors in the field of oncological research. The study found evidence for the

continuously increasing representation of women as senior authors and authors of single-authored articles. However, gender disparity still exists in oncological research, especially in the first author position. Female-female authorship pattern showed the most obvious increase relative to other gender-wise authorship patterns.

Hosseini and Sharifzad (2021) analyzed the publication and citation records of men and women researchers in Ireland. The quantitative analysis revealed that women researchers had fewer publications and received fewer citations per person and participated less often in international collaborations. The participated women researchers believed that their opportunities for research engagements are negatively impacted by their gender roles and family responsibilities.

Chary *et al.*, (2021) conducted a study on gender bias against women researchers in scientific publications and citations. The study explored that the senior female authors have achieved gender parity in the first authorship and male senior authors show a significant decrease in the FFA-Index compared to the productivity of female senior authors.

Vinay and Sampath Kumar (2021) investigated the research productivity of male and female authors in LIS research. The result of the study showed that there has been an increasing proposition of female authors over the years with the resulting decline of male authors.

In a recent review, Kwiek and Roszka (2022) explored the gender disparity in the international research collaboration of Polish scientists. Female scientists exhibit a higher rate of general, national, and institutional collaboration, and male scientists exhibit a higher rate of international collaboration.

The literature review indicates that there is gender disparity in the research productivity in various subjects.

Objectives of the Study

The study has been conducted with the following research objectives:

- To identify the nature of authorship patterns in Indian LIS scholarly literature.
- To examine the relationship between the research productivity and professional engagement of authors.
- To know the research productivity of male and female authors in LIS research.

Hypotheses

H1. There is a positive correlation between the number of articles and authors.

H2. There is a significant difference between the male and female authors' productivity.

H3. There is an association between the authors' gender and professional engagements.

Scope of the Study

The study is based on the research works published over ten years (2012 to 2021) in three prominent Library and Information Science journals viz.,

1. SRELS Journal of Information Management
2. World Digital Libraries – An International Journal
3. KELPRO Bulletin.

The above UGC care list journals have been considered for the study since they have a long traditional history of scholarly publications in the Indian LIS discipline. A total of 851 articles including research articles, case studies, review articles, and technical papers were studied from the perspective of the authors' gender and the influence of gender was assessed concerning individual and collaborative

levels. Biographical notes provided at the end of each article and authors' details given on the first page were the chief source of information regarding the respective the author's gender, affiliation, university, and state/country.

Methodology

The required details were extracted from the articles and saved in a separate MS- Excel file for further analysis. The details regarding the number of articles, authorship pattern, and author productivity are collected to fulfill the stated research objectives. Furthermore, the professional status of authors has been analyzed under four categories: LIS teachers, LIS professionals (including Chief Librarian, Librarian, Deputy Librarian, Assistant Librarian, and Library and Information Assistant), Research scholars, and Others (Technical Officers, PG students, Managers, Directors, Scientists, etc.). Further, the SPSS (version 26) was used for statistical analysis.

Data Analysis and Interpretation

Table-1: Productivity of Male and Female authors in LIS Research

Year	Number of Articles	Number of Authors	Male	AMPP	Female	AFPP
2012	98	175	123	1.25	52	0.53
2013	104	183	121	1.16	62	0.59
2014	75	149	110	1.46	39	0.52
2015	90	156	112	1.24	44	0.48
2016	95	188	143	1.50	45	0.47
2017	84	150	115	1.41	35	0.41
2018	80	154	111	1.38	43	0.53
2019	77	146	113	1.46	33	0.42
2020	72	140	105	1.45	35	0.48
2021	76	139	95	1.25	44	0.57
Total	851	1580	1148	1.34	432	0.50

*AMPP= Average Male Author Per Paper * AFPP=Average Female Author Per Paper

Table- 1 reveals a total of 851 papers published between 2012 and 2021. During the study period, 1580 authors contributed to selected LIS journals. Of these 1148 authors are males and 432 are females. The Pearson correlation indicates that there is a highly positive correlation between the number of articles and the number of authors ($r=.915$), and the correlation is significant ($p=.000$), it is found that the number of articles written by female authors is comparatively less when compared to male authors. Therefore, based on the statistical result it may be concluded that the H1 is accepted. To identify the difference between the number of articles vs male authors' productivity, the number of articles vs female authors' productivity, and male vs female authors' productivity the t-test has been applied. The result shows that there is a significant difference between the number of articles written by the number of articles vs male authors' productivity ($t=-10.127$, $p=.000$) and the number of articles vs female authors' productivity ($t=21.721$, $p=.000$), and the number of male authors vs female authors productivity ($t=17.836$, $p=.000$). Hypothesis-2 "There is a significant difference between the male and female authors' productivity" has been accepted. It is found that the overall average of the male author is 1.34 during the study period. While AFPP is highest at 0.59 in 2013 and lowest at 0.41 in the year 2017 with an overall average female author being 0.50 during the study period.

Table- 2: Year-wise authorship pattern of Indian LIS research

Year	Number of Articles	Number of Authors	Solo author	Two authors	Three authors	Four authors	Five and above authors
2012	98	175	40	43	13	0	2
2013	104	183	39	51	14	0	0
2014	75	149	19	42	12	0	2
2015	90	156	36	45	7	1	1
2016	95	188	32	42	14	6	1
2017	84	150	31	42	9	2	0
2018	80	154	23	44	10	2	1
2019	77	146	23	40	12	1	1
2020	72	140	15	47	9	1	0
2021	76	139	28	36	9	3	0
Total	851	1580	286 (33.60)	432 (50.76)	109 (12.80)	16 (1.88)	8 (0.94)

Note: The number within the parenthesis indicates the percentage

Table- 2 depicts the authorship pattern in library and information science scholarly journal articles. The data shows that two authored papers are top of the list with 432 articles (50.76 %) followed by the single-authored papers (33.60%), three authored papers (12.80%) and four authored papers (1.88%). Hence it is revealed that collaborative research has dominated the field of library and information science scholarly research.

Table-3: Authorship pattern cross-tabulated by gender

Year	Number of Articles	Male	Female	Male – Male	Male – Female	Female- Female	Female - Male
2012	98	28	12	33	5	8	12
2013	104	27	12	32	12	10	11
2014	75	14	5	27	7	4	18
2015	90	27	9	28	6	5	15
2016	95	25	8	36	6	6	14
2017	84	24	7	30	6	4	13
2018	80	16	7	31	7	3	16
2019	77	18	5	33	6	5	10
2020	72	14	1	30	10	7	10
2021	76	21	7	24	9	8	7
Total	851	214 (25.14)	73 (8.75)	304 (35.72)	74 (8.69)	60 (7.05)	126 (14.80)

Note: The number within the parenthesis indicates the percentage

Table- 3 reveals the different combinations of gender-wise authorship patterns of LIS researchers. Two combinations involve an author's work at individual levels and four combinations represent the involvement of authors in groups. The table depicts that most of the articles are written by male-male authors (35.72%), followed by male-only authors (25.14%) and female and male authors (14.80%). The table indicates that the male authors are more productive in LIS research whether they worked as an individual as well as in a collaborative. Further, it can be seen in the table research productivity of female authors is lower when they work at the individual level or in collaboration with other female authors in LIS research in India.

Table-4: Journal wise authorship pattern cross-tabulated by gender

Name of the Journal	Number of Articles	Male	Female	Male – Male	Male - Female	Female- Female	Female - Male
The SRELS Journal of Information Management	546 (64.15)	150 (27.47)	36 (6.59)	197 (36.08)	57 (10.43)	29 (5.31)	77 (14.10)
World Digital Libraries: An International Journal (WDL)	103 (12.10)	33 (32.03)	7 (6.79)	41 (39.80)	7 (6.79)	8 (7.76)	7 (6.79)
KELPRO Bulletin	202 (23.73)	31 (15.34)	30 (14.85)	66 (32.67)	10 (4.95)	23 (11.38)	42 (20.79)
Total	851	214 (25.14)	73 (8.57)	304 (35.72)	74 (8.69)	60 (7.05)	126 (14.80)

Note: The number within the parenthesis indicates the percentage

Further, the study tried to identify the journals wise authorship pattern cross-tabulated by gender. The data presented in table-4 clearly shows that most of the contributions are coming from the combination of male-male authors (35.72%), followed by male-only authors (25.14%) and female as first authors along with male authors (14.80%). It clearly shows that female authors are underrepresented whether they work at individual levels or collaborative.

Table-5: Research productivity and the professional engagements of male and female LIS researchers.

Designation	Total Number of Authors	Male	Female
LIS Professionals **	579	422 (72.88)	157 (27.11)
LIS Teacher	536	430 (80.22)	106 (19.77)
Research Scholar	204	112 (54.90)	92 (45.09)
Others*	261	184 (70.49)	77 (29.50)
Total	1580	1148 (72.65)	432 (27.34)

Note: The number within the parenthesis indicates the percentage

* Technical officers, PG students, Managers, Directors Etc.

** Librarian, Deputy Librarian, Assistant Librarian, and Library and Information Assistants

Table 5 shows the research productivity and the professional engagements of male and female LIS researchers. It is evident from the table that the male authors dominated over female authors even as LIS teachers (80.22%) as well as LIS professionals (72.88%) and research scholars (54.90%). To substantiate this data, the Chi-square test has been employed. The test indicates that there is a significant association between the research productivity and professional engagements of male and female authors ($\chi^2 = 61.648$, $p = .000$). Hypothesis-3 "There is an association between the authors' gender and professional engagements" has been accepted.

Table- 6: Annual Growth Rate of Female Contribution

Year	Female authors contribution	Annual Growth Rate
2012	52	0
2013	62	19.23
2014	39	-37.09
2015	44	12.82
2016	45	2.27
2017	35	-22.22
2018	43	22.85
2019	33	-23.25
2020	35	6.06
2021	44	25.71

Table-6 shows the annual growth rate of publication of female authors in the Indian Library and Information Science scholarly journals during the period 2012 to 2021. The formula for calculation of Annual Growth Rate (AGR) given by Kumar and Kaliyaperumal (2015) was used to calculate AGR, and it is as follows:

$$AGR = \frac{\text{End Value} - \text{First Value}}{\text{First Value}} \times 100$$

The analysis resolved that the highest AGR of 25.71 for female authors was recorded in the year 2021, followed by 22.85 in the year 2018 and 19.23 in the year 2013. The lowest AGR was -37.09 for female authors recorded in the year 2014, followed by 23.25 in the year 2019 and -22.22 in the year 2017.

Discussion and Conclusion

In the present study, it was shown that the female authors are less productive compared to their male counterparts in Indian library and information science scholarly literature it is clearly shown in the study that female authors contributed only 27.34% of articles during the study period at the same time the male authors are contributed 72.65% of articles. The overall average of the male author is 1.34 and the overall average for female authors per paper is 0.50 during the study period. It evidently indicates that

female authors are underrepresented more than their male counterparts in Indian LIS research.

The authorship pattern reveals a remarkable difference between the number of single authors and multiple authors. The authorship pattern shows that collaborative research (66.39%) is predominated over the solo authorship pattern (33.60%) in Indian LIS research. The Pearson correlation test clearly indicates that there is a highly positive correlation between the number of articles and the number of

authors ($r=.915$), and the correlation is significant ($p=.000$). The study opined that team research is favored in library and information science research in India.

The result of the study found that most of the works are produced by a team comprising male-male authors (35.72%) in LIS research. Further, it can be seen in the study research productivity of female authors is lower when they work at the individual level (8.75%) or in collaboration with other female authors (7.05%) in LIS research in India.

Regarding the professional engagement of authors, LIS professionals are found to be more productive as compared to others. From the above discussion, it is recommended that female LIS professionals need to work on improving their research output. The enabling and conducive environments may be created to support female authors to carry out research and publish their research works. In this context, government organizations, universities, and college authorities may encourage to provide research grants to support research among female authors.

In conclusion, this study highlighted gender disparities in research productivity in the field of library and information science across the country. For the whole cohort, male authors had a higher number of publications than women and a higher percentage of first and last authorship in collaborative research works.

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